

ADULTERATION: A MAJOR CHALLENGE ASSOCIATED WITH *O. OCTANDRA* IN THE TRADITIONAL SYSTEM OF MEDICINE IN SRI LANKA

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ABSTRACT

Adulterants and substitutes are common malpractices in herbal medicine. Confusion in vernacular names, Lack of knowledge of herbal plants, similarity in morphology and color, and unavailability of authentic plants are some of the reasons for adulteration of medicinal plants. *Osbeckia octandra* (L.) DC, which belongs to the family Melastomataceae, known as “*Heen bovitiya*” is an endemic plant to Sri Lanka and is widely used in traditional medicine, especially to treat jaundice and other liver disorders. One of the significant drawbacks of using *O. octandra* in the traditional therapeutic system in Sri Lanka is adulteration. This study was conducted to identify the most common adulterants of *O. octandra* and to determine how *O. octandra* can be morphologically differentiated from other adulterants. *O. aspera* and *M. malabathricum* have been identified as available adulteration materials for *O. octandra*. Both *O. aspera* and *M. malabathricum* are often misidentified by the public as *O. octandra* due to their similar vernacular

names and morphological characteristics. According to the results, the species can be clearly distinguished from *O. octandra* and *O. aspera* using morphological characters. *M. malabathricum* was clearly separated from *O. octandra* and *O. aspera* in the TLC profile of ethanol extracts in the solvent systems of Hexane.

KEYWORDS: *Osbeckia octandra*, Adulterations, Traditional Medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Adulterants and substitutes are common malpractices in herbal medicine. Adulteration is defined as a practice of substituting the original crude drug partially or wholly with other similar-looking substances that are either free from or inferior in chemical and therapeutic properties, or the addition of low-grade or spoiled drugs, or entirely different drugs like the of original drug, with the intention of enhancing profits. (Kokate et al., 2007 and Mukherjee et al., 2002).

Direct or intentional adulteration is deliberate and usually involves substituting an herbal drug, in whole or in part, with inferior products. Due to morphological resemblance to the authentic herb, many inferior commercial varieties are used as adulterants—unintentional adulteration that sometimes occurs without the bad intention of the manufacturer's or supplier's evil intent. Sometimes, in the absence of proper means of evaluation, an authentic drug, partially or entirely devoid of its active ingredients, may enter the market. Confusion in vernacular names, Lack of knowledge of herbal plants, similarity in morphology and color, and unavailability of authentic plants are some of the reasons for adulteration of medicinal plants. (Raviraja Shetty, G., and Harsha, R., 2021).

According to Senarathna (2001), *Osbeckia octandra* (L.) DC, a member of the family Melastomataceae known as "Vern: *Heen bovitiya*," is an endemic plant to Sri Lanka and is widely used in traditional medicine. *O. octandra* is a plant used in traditional medicine to treat jaundice and other liver disorders. (Renée et al., 2008).

One of the significant drawbacks of *O. octandra* in the traditional therapeutic system is adulteration. People often misuse this plant because they lack proper knowledge of identifying *O. octandra*, as it has purple flowers, and most of the flowers of the *Osbeckia* species have purple flowers. Promoting awareness of the appropriate identification of *O. octandra* would help ensure the correct plant is selected for medicinal purposes. This study was conducted to identify the most common adulterants of *O. octandra* and to determine how *O. octandra* can be morphologically differentiated from other adulterants.

METHODOLOGY

The literature survey was conducted using electronic databases such as Elsevier-Science Direct, PubMed, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate. Keywords such as "*Osbeckia octandra*", "adulteration", "Traditional medicine", and "morphological features" were used to search for

research articles. The research articles published up to April 2025 were included in the study. Studies focusing on the adulteration of *O. octandra* are included in the study. Articles not related to adulterations were excluded. Limited amounts of research have been conducted on the adulteration of *O. octandra* plant. Mainly used adulteration plants were selected, and their morphological features were studied to differentiate them.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Osbeckia octandra, a flowering plant from the Melastomataceae family, is native to Sri Lanka and is known locally as "*Heen Bovitiya*." It thrives in tropical regions and is often found along forest edges, in grasslands, and in scrublands. This shrub produces violet-petaled flowers with characteristic yellow stamens and can grow up to 1.2 meters in height. It has elliptic leaves that feel scratchy due to their distinctive pubescent texture.

Heen bovitiya (Osbeckia octandra) is well known as a liver tonic, and the plant's leaves are mainly used. Most people in rural areas of Sri Lanka add *Heen bovitiya* leaves to their fresh salads to help control their blood sugar levels. *Kolakenda* (Herbal porridge) made up of *Heen bovitiya* has been recommended for patients who are suffering from diabetes and hepatitis in Sri Lankan Indigenous medicine (Jayaweera, 1982).

There are about 50 species in the genus *Osbeckia* L, which is primarily found in Asia. (Pulpra, Prashob., 2019). *O. octandra* is a small shrub that belongs to the *Melastomataceae* family. *O. octandra* is native to Sri Lanka, and it has been introduced into Mauritius. (Vivekanandarajah et al., 2024). Dassanayaka (1996) states that this plant species is distributed across the country's dry, wet, and montane zones. It is commonly called the Ayurveda bush-tree, Heen Bovitiya in Sinhala, Katthoo mukthohulai in Tamil, and Eight Stamen *Osbeckia* in English. It is an erect, more branched shrublet which is about 2 m in height with 4-angled stems covered with strigose or velutinous hairs. Leaves are 1.5-6 cm in size. They are opposite, entire, strigose or sub coriaceous in shape and have 3-5 nerves (Ediriweera and Ratnasooriya, 2009).

O. octandra has been used in Sri Lankan Ayurvedic medicine to treat diabetes, hemorrhoids, hepatitis, ascites, jaundice, other liver disorders, and hyperlipidemia (Jayaweera, 1980). *O. octandra* is a plant used in traditional medicine to treat jaundice and other liver disorders. (Renée et al, 2008). Furthermore, Wijerathna et al. (2014) state that the leaves, bark, and

roots of this plant are used in Ayurveda to treat diabetes mellitus, hemorrhoids, hepatitis, ascites, liver disorders, jaundice, and hyperlipidemia.

This plant is well-known to have antidiabetic, anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-mutagenic, anticlastogenic, anti-aggregate, antispasmodic, anti-anemic, analgesic, hepatoprotective, anesthetic and immune-stimulant properties (Thabrew and Jayatilaka, 1999; Perera *et al.*, 2013).

O. octandra leaves are rich in many phytochemicals: phenols, flavonoids, tannins, diterpenes, terpenoids, phytosterols, saponins, alkaloids, carbohydrates, proteins, and amino acids. (Hettihewa & Silva, 2021).

O. aspera and *M. malabathricum* have been identified as available adulteration materials for *O. octandra*. (Wijesinghe, S.R.K.S., 2021).

Osbeckia octandra and *Osbeckia aspera* are two very closely related plant species belonging to the family Melastomaceae, found in Sri Lanka (Dassanayake, 1996). They are both referred to as "*Heen bovitiya*" by the local population and are used in the traditional medicine of alleviate jaundice associated with liver disease. (Jayaweera, 1982).

O. octandra can be adulterated with plant materials that resemble the morphological, chemical, and therapeutic characteristics of the authentic plant. According to reports, *Osbeckia aspera*, referred to as "*Bovitiya*," belongs to the same family, is found in Sri Lanka, and is used in traditional medicine of alleviate jaundice-related liver diseases. *Melastoma malabathricum*, known as "*Maha bovitiya*", or "*Bovitiya*" by the local population, is also used in traditional medicine. Both *O. aspera* and *M. malabathricum* are often misidentified by the general public as *O. octandra* due to their similar vernacular names and morphological characteristics. (Senarathne, 2001). Wijesinghe & Priyadarshan (2022) investigated the morphological characteristics and phytochemical properties of *O. octandra* in the presence of available adulterants, namely *Osbeckia aspera* and *Melastoma malabathricum*. According to the results, the species can be clearly distinguished from *O. octandra* and *O. aspera* using morphological characters. *M. malabathricum* was clearly separated from *O. octandra* and *O. aspera* in the TLC profile of ethanol extracts in the solvent systems of Hexane. (Wijesinghe & Priyadarshan, 2022).

Image 3 - *M. malabathricum*.

Table 1: Key morphological character comparison of *O. octandra*, *O. aspera*, and *M. malabathricum* Sources - (Wijesinghe & Priyadarshan, 2022)

Character	<i>O. octandra</i>	<i>O. aspera</i>	<i>M. malabathricum</i>
Shape of leaf	Elliptic	Elliptic to ovate	Elliptic
Arrangement of leaves	Opposite	Whorled	Alternate
Shape of the leaf base	Rounded to acute	Rounded to acute	Acute to obtuse
Shape of the leaf apex	Acute	Acute to Acuminate	Acute or Acuminate
Color of petals	Pink to mauve and violet	Pink to mauve and violet	Pink to mauve and violet
Shape of sepals	Triangular	Triangular to ovate	Ovate-triangular
Color of stamens	Yellow	Yellow	Pink
Fruit type	Dry capsule	Dry capsule	Ovoid fleshy capsule

CONCLUSION

O. aspera and *M. malabathricum* have been identified as available adulteration materials for *O. octandra*. *O. octandra* and *O. aspera* are two very closely related plant species found in Sri Lanka. They are both referred to as "*Heen bovitiya*" by the local population and are both used in traditional medicine for the alleviation of jaundice related to liver disease. *Melastoma malabathricum* known as "*Maha bovitiya*", or "*Bovitiya*" by the local population is also used in traditional medicine. Both *O. aspera* and *M. malabathricum* tend to get misidentified as *O.*

octandra by general public, due to their similar vernacular names and morphological characteristics. According to the results they have stated that the species can be clearly distinguished from *O. octandra* and *O. aspera* using morphological characters. *M. malabathricum* was clearly separated from *O. octandra* and *O. aspera* in TLC profile of ethanol extracts in solvent systems of Hexane.

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